

**MENTAL HEALTH ASSOCIATION
OF SOUTH-EASTERN EUROPE**

**“LUCIAN BLAGA” UNIVERSITY SIBIU
FACULTY OF MEDICINE**

**“LUCIAN BLAGA” UNIVERSITY SIBIU
FACULTY OF SOCIAL AND HUMAN SCIENCES**

**“DR. GHEORGHE PREDA”
PSYCHIATRIC HOSPITAL SIBIU**

**2ND EASTERN EUROPEAN
CONFERENCE
OF MENTAL HEALTH**

IN AND OUT OF YOUR MIND

**SIBIU, ROMANIA
27 – 30 SEPTEMBER
2018**

ABSTRACT BOOK

EDITURA UNIVERSITATII LUCIAN BLAGA SIBIU

ISBN:978-606-12-1569-0

"LUCIAN BLAGA" UNIVERSITY SIBIU
FACULTY OF MEDICINE
FACULTY OF SOCIAL AND HUMAN SCIENCES

MENTAL HEALTH ASSOCIATION
OF SOUTH-EASTERN EUROPE

"DR. GHEORGHE PREDA"
PSYCHIATRIC HOSPITAL SIBIU

2ND EASTERN EUROPEAN CONFERENCE OF MENTAL HEALTH

IN AND OUT OF YOUR MIND

SIBIU, ROMANIA
27 - 30 SEPTEMBER 2018

ABSTRACT BOOK

EDITURA UNIVERSITATII LUCIAN BLAGA SIBIU

ISBN:978-606-12-1569-0

"LUCIAN BLAGA" UNIVERSITY SIBIU
FACULTY OF MEDICINE
FACULTY OF SOCIAL AND HUMAN SCIENCES

MENTAL HEALTH ASSOCIATION
OF SOUTH-EASTERN EUROPE

"DR. GHEORGHE PREDA"
PSYCHIATRIC HOSPITAL SIBIU

**2ND EASTERN EUROPEAN CONFERENCE OF MENTAL HEALTH
IN AND OUT OF YOUR MIND
SIBIU, ROMANIA 27 – 30 SEPTEMBER 2018**

President of Conference

Howard H. Goldman (USA)

President of Scientific Committee

Germain Weber (Austria)

President of Local Organizing Committee

Mihaela Cernusca Mitariu (Romania)

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Dragos Ovidiu Alexandru (Romania)
Mohammed Al Sbou (Jordan)
Hiroaki Ambo (Japan)
Ciprian Bacila (Romania)
Mihaela Dana Bucuta (Romania)
Jana Chihai (Moldova)
Ariel Como (Albania)
Doina Cozman (Romania)
Catalina Crisan (Romania)
Lisa Dixon (USA)
Lavinia Duica (Romania)
Donald Goff (USA)
Heinz Katschnig (Austria)

Maria Ladea (Romania)
Davor Mucic (Denmark)
Mihai Mutica (Romania)
Vladimir Nakov (Bulgaria)
Joachim Nitschke (Germany)
Mihail Cristian Pirlog (Romania)
Marco Sarchiapone (Italy)
Vaska Stancheva-Popkostadinova (Bulgaria)
Raluca Sassu (Romania)
Sonila Tomori (Albania)
Cristian Vasile (Romania)
Josko Viskic (Croatia)
Tea Vukusic-Rukavina (Croatia)

LOCAL ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Irina Antonescu
Ciprian Bacila
Doriana Nicoleta Basaraba
Amine Ben Salem Mohamed
Viorica Bobic
Mihaela Dana Bucuta
Simona Butnarusu
Adrian Brate
Delia Cazacu
Gabriel Cazacu

Ioana Amalia Cernusca Mitariu
Anca Iulia Ciobanu
Lavinia Duica
Mihaela Ioana
Andra Ionescu
Monica Itu
Ionut Mirzoi
Corneliu Moşoiu
Cristina Neamtu
Cristian Nicoara

Gratiela Olteanu
Elena Daciana Pintilie
Adela Popa
Cornelia Florina Puiu
Sorin Radu
Valentina Denisa Sandu
Ionela Madalina Stanciu
Laura Stef
Alin Gilbert Sumedrea
Diana Vulea

SUBSTANCE USE AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD

S Harhaji^{1,2}, V Mijatović Jovanović^{1,2}, I Radić^{1,2}, S Ukropina^{1,2}, N Dragnić^{1,2}, S Čanković^{1,2}

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia.

²Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia.

Introduction: Unhealthy life habits acquired at a young age significantly impact the health in the short and long term. According to the Global Burden of Disease, Injuries, and Risk Factors Study 2013, tobacco and alcohol use are among the leading risk factors for premature death and morbidity worldwide. The objective of our research was to analyze habits of psychoactive substance use (tobacco, alcohol, illicit drugs) among medical students.

Methods: The study was conducted at the Faculty of Medicine in Novi Sad during the academic year 2013/2014, as part of the project “Risk behaviors of students related to reproductive health”. The research included 778 students out of 1143 students of the first and the third year of all study programs (medicine, dentistry, pharmacy, nursing, medical rehabilitation and special rehabilitation and education). Self-administered questionnaire has been used.

Results and discussion: Every fourth student smoked cigarettes occasionally or daily (25.1%), without difference regarding gender. Smoking was more frequent among students from urban than from rural settlements (27.8% vs. 18.0%; $p=0.005$). Every second student (56.6%) consumed 6 or more alcohol drinks per occasion more than once in a year (76.6% males and 51.5% females; $p<0.001$). This pattern of drinking was more prevalent in smokers compared to nonsmokers (81.4% vs. 48.3%; $p<0.001$). Illicit drugs used 10.3% of students at least once in a lifetime with significant gender difference (17.2% males and 8.5% females; $p=0.001$). Illicit drug abuse was more frequent among smokers than students who never smoked (25.4% vs. 5.2%; $p<0.001$). Psychoactive substance use in medical students is concerning, especially among males, as well as the simultaneous use of different types of psychoactive substances.

Research support: The research was funded by *Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research*.

